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**The Role Of Extracurricular Activities In Educating A Socially Active Person
Based On Moral Values****Raxmatova Dinora Isomovna**

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role and importance of extracurricular activities in the formation of a socially active person based on moral values, namely, such organizational forms as circles, club activities, poetry readings and debates, and moral and educational events. It is argued that through extracurricular activities, high moral qualities such as patriotism, honesty, diligence, kindness, and solidarity can be formed in students.

Keywords: Moral values, upbringing, extracurricular activities, circle, spiritual upbringing, pedagogical approach, integration of education and upbringing.

Introduction.

The development of each society depends, first of all, on its moral foundation and the social consciousness of people formed on this foundation. In today's era of globalization, the speed of information flow, and increased intercultural influence, the formation of a stable moral position in the younger generation and their preparation for active participation in social life have become an important task. Because a person can become a truly useful person for society if he is not only educated, but also spiritually mature and has moral criteria.

On this path, it is not enough to be limited to the lesson process alone. Extracurricular activities are of great importance in the comprehensive development of the student's personality - that is, circles on various topics, poetry readings and discussions, cultural and educational events, practical projects and volunteer activities. Through these activities, young people not only enrich their knowledge, but also practically feel moral values in communication, cultivate such qualities as teamwork, valuing the opinions of others, and a sense of responsibility.

So, extracurricular activities are a kind of educational school. There, the student learns from life, not from the teacher. Moral values take on a practical form. It is through these activities that we educate socially conscious, spiritually rich, patriotic and enterprising young people. This article analyzes the role and importance of extracurricular activities in moral education.

Methodology:

Whatever methods and approaches are used in human education, they should all be well thought out, goal-oriented and consistent. Especially in such a complex and delicate process as the formation of a socially active person based on moral values, the methodological approaches chosen should be reasonable and close to life. In this article, the methodological basis of the study was taken as the basis of a systematic approach, an

activity-oriented approach, and the principles of person-oriented education.

A systematic approach allows us to see moral education not only as a separate phenomenon, but as a component of the entire educational process. Moral values should not be limited to individual topics in the curriculum, but should be instilled naturally in every activity, in every extracurricular activity. It is through such consistency and coherence that moral qualities are deeply embedded in the student's mind.

An activity-oriented approach awakens in students the need not only to acquire knowledge, but also to apply it in practice, to feel useful in society. Extracurricular activities create exactly such opportunities: through role-playing games, theatrical scenes, discussions, social projects, the student tests his moral views in life, understands his place in the community, and feels social responsibility.

The methodology of a person-oriented approach is based on the appropriate pedagogical influence on each student, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student. Each student participates in extracurricular activities depending on his interests, needs and inner spiritual world. Therefore, educational work should not be just a mandatory plan, but a process related to the student's inner world. Also, in writing this article, methods of comparison, analysis, observation and practical activity study were used. Based on pedagogical experience and existing methodological developments, an attempt was made to assess the effectiveness of extracurricular activities.

Discussion.

Today's youth are the driving force of tomorrow's society. As their moral views, social activity and civic position are formed, society will be formed accordingly. From this point of view, extracurricular activities are becoming not only a factor complementing the educational process, but also a powerful tool for educational influence. Because it is in the extracurricular environment that the student thinks freely, expresses himself freely and begins to understand his social position.

For example, a student participating in the "Patriotic Circle" not only hears about our history and the sacrifice of our ancestors, but also feels their lives through stage performances, fostering a sense of pride in himself. Or through the "Ethics Lessons" club, students understand the practical reflection of values such as honesty, humanity, and patience in life. The role of the teacher in these processes is important - he becomes not only a person who gives knowledge, but also an inspirer, a guide, and a person who finds a way to the heart.

Through extracurricular activities, the student begins to feel his social responsibility: he can speak in a team, justify his opinion, participate in debates, hear criticism, and most importantly, learn to value the opinions of others. This is the basis of moral education. Because a person who understands not only himself, but also others is a socially active person. Also, moral values are taught not only through propaganda, but also through

personal example. During extracurricular activities, students form behavioral criteria in themselves, depending on the moral position of their teachers, friends, and the team. This is the most effective form of direct influence. In extracurricular activities, such an influence is felt more strongly, because it takes place in a free, unconventional, creative environment.

Conclusion.

The criterion of human maturity is in his morality. The educational process is the most important stage that lays the foundation of this morality. Instilling high moral values, especially in the hearts of the younger generation, is the duty not only of the teacher, but also of the entire society. In this sense, extracurricular activities - circles, clubs, staged events, spiritual and educational conversations - are one of the most effective tools in this regard. In extracurricular activities, the student learns to express himself, think independently, communicate in a team. This forms his moral thinking, social activity and sense of personal responsibility. Most importantly, during these activities, the student enriches his life views, understands values, finds his "I". Therefore, the process of moral education cannot be limited to lessons alone. Instilling moral values in young people through real examples, involving them as active participants, creating opportunities for them to think freely and try in practice is the real key to education. Extracurricular activities provide just such opportunities.

In conclusion, extracurricular activities not only promote moral qualities, but also instill them in the minds of young people, make them feel and live. As a result of this process, we educate young people who are active in social life, spiritually rich, and committed to moral standards. After all, a moral person is the most invaluable asset of society.

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